

Process-based constraints are not sufficient: evaluating their role in combination with state variable-based constraints on aerosol–cloud radiative forcing

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Abstract. Atmospheric aerosols and their interactions with clouds remain one of the largest sources of uncertainty in estimates of effective radiative forcing from aerosol–cloud interactions (ΔF_{aci}). While perturbed parameter ensembles (PPEs) have been used to explore and constrain this uncertainty using observed state variables, recent work has proposed process-based constraints, such as the slope of the relationship between cloud droplet number concentration (N_d) and liquid water path (L), as potentially more informative indicators. Here we evaluate the effectiveness of the N_d – L slope as a process-based constraint using the UKESM1 model across three climatically distinct marine regions, and compare it with a previously established state-variable-based constraint. The slope primarily constrains uncertainty associated with physical atmosphere parameters, while state-based observations constrain aerosol emissions and processes. However, the slope constraint alone produces only small reductions in N_d , L , and ΔF_{aci} uncertainty. Combining the slope and state-based observations further constrains ΔF_{aci} beyond the state-based constraint alone (up to an additional 36% reduction in uncertainty). However, the combined constraint appears to rely on compensating parameter effects, highlighting structural limitations in the model representation of aerosol–cloud interactions. Our results show that process-based constraints provide complementary information to state-variable constraints, but cannot be used in isolation to meaningfully constrain ΔF_{aci} . Specifically, combining process-based and state-variable constraints reveals structural deficiencies in current climate models, indicating that reducing uncertainty in ΔF_{aci} ultimately requires improved representation of aerosol–cloud coupling.

1 Introduction

Atmospheric aerosols play a crucial role in Earth’s climate system. They influence energy balance both directly, by scattering or absorbing sunlight, and indirectly, by acting as cloud condensation nuclei (CCN), which alter cloud properties and lifetimes (Seinfeld and Pandis, 2016). The aerosol–cloud interaction component of effective radiative forcing (ΔF_{aci}) is the largest source of uncertainty in anthropogenic effective radiative forcing (Carslaw, 2022; Forster et al., 2023).

A major source of uncertainty in estimates of ΔF_{aci} is how aerosol and cloud processes are represented in global climate models. Many of these processes occur on microphysical scales that cannot be resolved explicitly. As a result, they are described

using parameterizations, which are sets of equations designed to represent the statistical behaviour of sub-grid physical processes. These parameterizations introduce structural uncertainty, meaning errors that arise from imperfect or incomplete representations of physical processes within the model. Such uncertainties are difficult to quantify and cannot be fully mitigated through parameter tuning alone (Sexton et al., 2012). Consequently, reducing uncertainty in ΔF_{aci} remains challenging. Even with increasing model resolution, mismatches in spatial and temporal scales, observational limitations, and persistent model biases (arising from missing processes or the choice of parameterizations) limit our ability to narrow uncertainty in ΔF_{aci} (Schutgens et al., 2017; Hoffmann et al., 2023; Liu et al., 2024; Price et al., 2025).

In particular, the cloud albedo effect, wherein increased cloud droplet number concentrations (N_d) enhance cloud reflectivity for a fixed liquid water path (L), is a dominant component of ΔF_{aci} . Because cloud reflectivity depends logarithmically on aerosol concentrations, much of the uncertainty in cloud albedo effect forcing arises from poorly constrained aerosol concentrations in the preindustrial atmosphere (Carslaw et al., 2013). These uncertainties in natural aerosol emissions, many of which are difficult or impossible to constrain observationally, propagate through climate models and contribute to persistent spread in estimates of aerosol–cloud radiative forcing (Johnson et al., 2020; Regayre et al., 2020).

Perturbed Parameter Ensembles (PPEs) provide a powerful framework for quantifying and constraining uncertainty in climate models, particularly in the context of ΔF_{aci} (Carslaw et al., 2013; Regayre et al., 2014). Rather than tuning a model toward a specific set of observations, PPEs systematically perturb dozens of uncertain physical parameters across their expert-elicited ranges (Lee et al., 2012; Regayre et al., 2023; Eidhammer et al., 2024; Bhatti et al., 2026). Using statistical emulators, PPEs can efficiently sample millions of parameter combinations, enabling diagnosis of how parameter uncertainty propagates to emergent properties, including observable (N_d and L) and non-observable (ΔF_{aci}) quantities (Lee et al., 2016; Yoshioka et al., 2019). When constrained with satellite observations, PPEs help identify which parameter combinations are consistent with observations and which sources of uncertainty dominate model behaviour (Regayre et al., 2014; Yoshioka et al., 2019; Regayre et al., 2018). This approach has proven especially useful in distinguishing uncertainty arising from aerosol emissions, cloud microphysics, and their interactions (Carslaw et al., 2013; Sansom et al., 2024), and in guiding the development of targeted observational constraints to reduce model spread (Regayre et al., 2023, 2026). For example, PPE-based constraints have been used to substantially reduce uncertainty in aerosol–radiation interactions through observational constraints on aerosol optical properties (e.g. Johnson et al., 2020), and to constrain aerosol–cloud interaction forcing over marine regions using satellite-based cloud property relationships (e.g. Regayre et al., 2023).

In addition to state variables, so-called "process-based" metrics have been extensively used to estimate the magnitude of ΔF_{aci} by relating observable cloud properties to underlying aerosol–cloud processes (Bellouin et al., 2020). One such relationship is the N_d – L relationship, which we characterize here as the slope of $\log L$ against $\log N_d$. This N_d – L slope is influenced by microphysical and dynamical processes that govern cloud adjustments and cloud development (Gryspeerd et al., 2019). The N_d – L slope is typically derived using a regression in log–log space and has been used to interpret how increases in aerosol loading alter cloud properties. Observational studies show that in clean environments, L initially increases with N_d because additional droplets suppress precipitation, producing a positive N_d – L slope. In more polluted regimes, however, L decreases with increasing N_d because the larger number of smaller droplets enhances evaporation during the entrainment of

dry air, producing a negative N_d-L slope (Gryspeerd et al., 2019; Murray-Watson and Gryspeerd, 2022). This “inverted-V” relationship is also apparent in satellite observations (e.g. from MODIS and AMSR-E), where the slope systematically varies with meteorological state variables such as lower-tropospheric stability and specific humidity (Gryspeerd et al., 2022; Murakami et al., 2021; Zhang et al., 2025), which indicates a link to the driving processes. Recent work suggests that much of this inverted-V sensitivity is driven not purely by aerosol-cloud microphysical feedbacks but by meteorological co-variability, that is, the tendency of both N_d and L to covary under shared meteorological influences such as boundary-layer depth, humidity, and stability (Zipfel et al., 2024; Goren et al., 2025; Christensen et al., 2022).

Several studies have attempted to use the N_d-L slope to estimate the strength of aerosol-cloud interactions and the L adjustment component of ΔF_{aci} . For instance, Bellouin et al. (2020) identified the N_d-L slope as one of the emergent relationships that could potentially reduce ΔF_{aci} uncertainty. However, natural experiments involving volcanic eruptions and ship tracks suggest that the observed N_d-L relationships may overestimate the true causal effect of anthropogenically driven increases in N_d on L due to the presence of confounding environmental factors (Gryspeerd et al., 2019). Gryspeerd et al. (2022) proposed a more robust approach by examining the temporal evolution of N_d and L over short time scales using MODIS overpasses. This method accounts for the initial cloud state and tracks the evolution of cloud properties, revealing both the direction and magnitude of their changes. This approach isolates the aerosol signal from correlated errors, but also highlights the high sensitivity of the N_d-L slope to initial meteorological conditions and retrieval uncertainties. Mülmenstädt et al. (2020, 2024) evaluated the N_d-L slope in several CMIP6-era global climate models, including version 1 of the UK Earth system Model (UKESM1). They found that although many models simulate a negative N_d-L slope comparable to observations in polluted environments, this relationship is not necessarily causal. When comparing present-day and preindustrial simulations that isolated aerosol effects, many models simulate an increase in L with increasing N_d , contradicting the observed negative slope. This suggests that while models may mimic observed patterns, the underlying mechanisms likely differ. That is, models may be right for the wrong reasons.

Observed relationships and overall differences between models have been evaluated in these studies; however, none have applied the N_d-L slope as a constraint, which we define as a narrowing of a quantified uncertainty range (Carslaw et al., 2025). Here, we evaluate the efficacy of the N_d-L slope as an observational constraint on a set of 1 million variants of UKESM1. We assess the capacity of the N_d-L slope to reduce uncertainty in N_d , L , and ΔF_{aci} , both individually and in combination with an established state-variable-based constraint (Regayre et al., 2023). These constraints are applied to three climatically distinct marine regions (Fig. 1), enabling targeted evaluation across contrasting aerosol regimes. In addition to output uncertainty, we analyze the effect of the constraints on model parameters to assess their physical consistency and to diagnose whether state- and process-based constraints can be meaningfully combined. Our results reveal both the potential and the pitfalls of N_d-L slope as a process-based emergent constraint, demonstrating that they provide meaningful insight only when the underlying model realistically represents the key physical processes involved in generating the N_d-L relationship.

Figure 1. Marine clusters used in this study, identified using K-means clustering based on the dominant drivers of uncertainty in ΔF_{aci} . Shown are the Northeast Atlantic (NEA), Eastern Tropical Atlantic (ETA), and Southeast Pacific (SEP) clusters analysed in this work. Adapted from Fig. 4 of Regayre et al. (2026)

90 2 Methodology

2.1 Model data

We use output from a perturbed parameter ensemble of the UKESM1 atmosphere-only configuration (UKESM1-A; Sellar et al. (2019)), as developed and described in Regayre et al. (2023). The ensemble consists of 221 members, each with a distinct combination of 37 uncertain aerosol and atmospheric process parameters. These parameters were selected based on prior
 95 sensitivity analyses and structural developments, with ranges determined through formal expert elicitation (Gosling, 2018). All simulations were performed using prescribed sea surface temperatures, sea ice, and anthropogenic emissions representative of the years 2014 (present-day) and 1850 (early-industrial), with horizontal winds nudged above approximately 2 km to ERA-Interim reanalysis over the period December 2016 to November 2017. Simulations use a horizontal resolution of N96 ($1.875^\circ \times 1.25^\circ$) and 85 vertical levels.

100 UKESM1-A includes the GLOMAP-mode aerosol scheme (Mann et al., 2010), the GA7.1 physical atmosphere (Walters et al., 2019) with a single-moment bulk cloud microphysics scheme, and the PC2 prognostic large-scale cloud (cloud fraction and condensate) scheme (Wilson et al., 2008), together with structural modifications to aerosol optical properties, wet scavenging, and boundary layer nucleation processes as described in Regayre et al. (2023). We analyze one year of output from each PPE member to evaluate N_d , L , and ΔF_{aci} in three climatically relevant marine regions. The output is grouped into four seasonal
 105 periods: December–February (DJF), March–May (MAM), June–August (JJA), and September–November (SON).

The clusters are defined using K-means clustering (Pedregosa et al., 2011) applied to the optimally constrained set of 5,000 model variants described in Regayre et al. (2026). Clustering was based on the proportional contributions of 37 perturbed model parameters to remaining uncertainty in ΔF_{aci} after state-based observational constraint, across more than 27,000 geographical locations. Therefore, model grid boxes within a cluster share common drivers of remaining ΔF_{aci} uncertainty across the
110 combined parameter perturbations.

From the Regayre et al. (2026) clusters, we selected three distinct marine clusters of persistent annual-mean ΔF_{aci} uncertainty. In these clusters, a substantial fraction of the original ΔF_{aci} uncertainty persists after application of the optimal constraint, although the magnitude varies regionally. Around 30 % remains in the Northeast Atlantic, while roughly 50 – 60 % persists in the Eastern Tropical Atlantic and around 70 – 80 % remains in the Southeast Pacific (Regayre et al., 2026, Fig. 2d). In absolute
115 terms, substantial uncertainty remains after constraint, with regional ΔF_{aci} ranges typically of order 3 – 5 W m^{-2} in North Atlantic regions and up to 4 – 10 W m^{-2} in persistent stratocumulus regions such as the Southeast Pacific. These wide ranges reflect the large unconstrained regional ΔF_{aci} uncertainty, meaning that substantial fractional reductions can leave considerable absolute uncertainty. The optimal constraint primarily affects a subset of parameters, most notably those controlling cloud droplet activation and primary sulfate emission size (Regayre et al., 2026). The optimal constraint primarily affects a subset of
120 parameters, most notably those controlling cloud droplet activation and primary sulfate emission size (Regayre et al., 2026). The remaining uncertainty arises from distinct parameter groups in each region. In the Northeast Atlantic, uncertainty is primarily associated with natural aerosol emissions (sea-salt and DMS), aerosol dry deposition, and cloud-top entrainment processes. In the Eastern Tropical Atlantic, cloud-top entrainment dominates, with additional contributions from natural aerosol emissions and sub-grid cloud heterogeneity parameters. In the Southeast Pacific, the remaining uncertainty is linked to sea-salt
125 emissions and cloud–radiation parameterizations, including parameters controlling autoconversion and sub-grid cloud structure (Regayre et al., 2026). These regional differences motivate the selection of these clusters as targets for additional process-based constraints. These clusters therefore represent key targets for additional process-based constraints. The three clusters analysed in this study are the Northeast Atlantic (NEA), Eastern Tropical Atlantic (ETA), and Southeast Pacific (SEP), and are shown in Fig. 1.

130 2.2 Satellite observations

We follow the observational approach described in Regayre et al. (2023) to compare cloud properties derived from the Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer (MODIS) with monthly mean model output. Physical and radiative cloud properties, including L , cloud optical depth (τ_c), and droplet effective radius (r_e), were obtained directly from MODIS instruments (King et al., 2003). To ensure consistent comparison with these observations, model-simulated quantities were processed using the
135 Cloud Feedback Model Intercomparison Project (CFMIP) MODIS satellite simulator (Bodas-Salcedo et al., 2011; Saponaro et al., 2020), which applies the same viewing geometry, retrieval assumptions, and sampling as the MODIS instrument. We derived N_d from τ_c and r_e under the assumption of a vertically uniform droplet number concentration, which is appropriate for stratocumulus regions (Grosvenor and Carslaw, 2020; Painemal and Zuidema, 2011).

All satellite measurements were regridded to match the model’s resolution and averaged by region and time. Monthly mean values of N_d and L were computed for the same three selected clusters used in the model analysis: NEA, ETA, and SEP.

2.3 N_d - L slope

For each of the three selected clusters, we calculate the relationship between N_d and L using seasonal (three-month) data for each member of the 221-member PPE described in Section 2.1, aggregating monthly mean values across all model grid boxes within each cluster. This approach differs from higher-resolution, near-instantaneous, pixel-scale sampling aggregated over long time periods that is commonly used in observational studies (Gryspeerd et al., 2019, 2022).

Despite the differences in sampling, these approaches produce the same overall average result (i.e. a observed similar slope). For example, applying this methodology to satellite-derived data yields consistently negative N_d - L slopes (Fig. 2f), in agreement with the behaviour reported using higher-resolution, pixel-scale approaches (Gryspeerd et al., 2019, 2022) in the same regions. In this study, we do not focus on the precise value of the slope itself, but rather on how it responds to parameter perturbations. For PPE-based constraint, the key requirement is that the diagnostic is sensitive to variations in model parameters. The N_d - L slope therefore remains informative even if part of the relationship reflects meteorological co-variability, since the PPE framework exploits systematic changes in the joint distribution of N_d and L across parameter space rather than relying on a purely causal interpretation. Aggregated data within each cluster are used to construct a joint-probability histogram, $P(L | N_d)$, which forms the basis for estimating the N_d - L slope. Figure 2 shows an example for December, January, and February 2016–17 in the NEA cluster, using five selected PPE members ($p = 0, 35, 89, 150, 210$) that span the range of slopes within the PPE. Similar figures for the ETA and SEP clusters, using the same time frame and selected members, are presented in the Supplement (Sections S1.2 and S1.3).

Previous analysis of this PPE showed that some cloud-property constraints are internally inconsistent within UKESM1-A. In particular, constraining model variants to match observed N_d degrades, or fails to improve, model agreement with observed L , while constraining model variants to match observed L does not produce consistent agreement with other cloud and radiative variables (Regayre et al., 2023). This inconsistency was interpreted as evidence of structural limitations in the model representation of cloud properties, particularly the coupling between cloud droplet number and cloud water in the single-moment microphysics scheme (Regayre et al., 2023). We therefore describe this behaviour as an inconsistency between constraint variables, following the terminology of ?. In the present study, our focus is not on constraining N_d or L as individual state variables, but on constraining the slope of the N_d - L relationship. This process-based metric may provide additional information about the mechanisms controlling aerosol–cloud interactions and forcing uncertainty. It also allows us to test whether the relationship between N_d and L is represented consistently enough to be combined with the existing state-variable-based constraint.

To account for the non-linear nature of the N_d - L relationship, we use the piecewise log-linear fitting method described by Gryspeerd et al. (2019). With this approach, L is related to N_d as:

$$\begin{aligned} \ln L &= \ln L^p + m_l (\ln N_d - \ln N_d^p), & \text{if } N_d < N_d^p \\ \ln L &= \ln L^p + m_h (\ln N_d - \ln N_d^p), & \text{if } N_d \geq N_d^p \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

Here, L^p and N_d^p denote the values at the intersection (or breakpoint) of the two linear segments (Fig. 2), while m_l and m_h denote the slopes of the low- N_d and high- N_d branches of the piecewise relationship, respectively. The breakpoint (N_d^p, L^p) is treated as a free parameter and is determined simultaneously with m_l and m_h by minimizing the residuals
175 between the fitted curve and the logarithmic $P(L | N_d)$ distribution. This piecewise function is fitted in log–log space using the Levenberg–Marquardt algorithm (Levenberg, 1944; Marquardt, 1963; Jones et al., 2001).

Figure 2. Variation in liquid water path (L) with respect to droplet number concentration (N_d) for the NEA cluster, based on monthly means for December, January, and February 2016–17, using five selected PPE members ($p = 0, 35, 89, 73, 161$; panels a–e). Panel (f) shows the probability density function of N_d-L slopes (m_h) across all 221 PPE members for the high N_d fit.

We then calculate the distribution of N_d-L slopes (m_h) across all 221 PPE members for the high N_d fit. The resulting probability density function is shown in Fig. 2f, alongside the slope obtained from satellite data. For consistency with observations, we focus solely on the high- N_d slope (m_h), since satellite data do not sufficiently sample the low- N_d regime to enable a reliable two-segment fit. As illustrated in the Supplement Figs. S4 (NEA), S6 (ETA), and S8 (SEP), MODIS retrievals exhibit limited coverage at low N_d , making single-segment fits more robust for comparison. While the N_d-L relationships for individual PPE

members are noisy, leading to low correlation coefficients, the ensemble distribution of slopes captures the spread in model behaviour and provides a robust measure of variability in the simulated aerosol–cloud interaction response.

185 The seasonal distributions of the high- N_d slope (m_h) across the full 221-member PPE are shown in Fig. 3 for DJF, MAM, JJA, and SON, together with the corresponding satellite-derived slope estimates. These distributions illustrate both the seasonal variability in the simulated N_d – L relationship and the position of the observational estimate relative to the ensemble spread, providing the basis for selecting the slope-based constraint applied in each region. For the application of the slope-based constraint, a single season is selected to exemplify constraint potential in each cluster based on the robustness of the observational estimate and its position relative to the ensemble distribution. Specifically, DJF is used for the NEA cluster,
190 MAM for the ETA cluster, and DJF for the SEP cluster. The selected season is then used to define the observational constraint applied to the emulated N_d – L slopes in each region.

Figure 3. Seasonal probability density functions of the high- N_d N_d - L slope (m_h) across all 221 PPE members for the NEA cluster. Panels show DJF, MAM, JJA, and SON. The dashed vertical line indicates the corresponding satellite-derived slope for each season.

2.4 Emulating the N_d - L Relationship

To extend the 221-member PPE, we use statistical Gaussian process emulators (O’Hagan, 2006) trained on the N_d - L slopes and the parameter values assigned to each PPE member. These emulators enable efficient sampling of the 37-dimensional parameter space and are used to estimate model responses for 1 million parameter combinations. Compared to generating additional climate model simulations, Gaussian process emulators are computationally efficient and explicitly represent uncertainty in their predictions. This uncertainty can be evaluated for any given parameter combination within the sampled parameter space,

providing a built-in assessment of emulator skill (relative to the model simulations) and helping to avoid over-constraining model output when comparing to observations (Lee et al., 2016; Regayre et al., 2018; Johnson et al., 2020; Heitmann et al., 2010; Higdon et al., 2008; Chang et al., 2016; Holden et al., 2010). As Gaussian process emulators are unconstrained statistical models, they can produce non-physical values for strictly positive variables such as N_d and L , particularly at the edges of parameter space. To ensure physical consistency, we impose a lower bound of zero on these variables in all analyses.

We first emulate the N_d - L slope (m_h) for each of the three selected clusters across each season (DJF, MAM, JJA, SON). In parallel, we emulate the monthly mean values of N_d , L , and ΔF_{aci} averaged across each cluster, using the same parameter combinations to generate one million samples for each variable. The emulated variables form the basis for applying observational constraints and evaluating the impact of reduced parameter uncertainty on aerosol-cloud interactions.

2.5 Observational constraints

We compare the unconstrained PPE with three constrained cases to assess how different observational constraints reduce uncertainty in ΔF_{aci} : (i) application of the N_d - L slope constraint for each individual cluster, (ii) the R23 constraint described in Regayre et al. (2023), based on multiple state-variable observations, and (iii) the combined application of the R23 and slope constraints (Table 1).

Each constraint defines a subset of model variants that most closely match the observations, and this subset is used to quantify uncertainty in N_d , L , and ΔF_{aci} within each cluster. Regayre et al. (2023), the R23 constraint retained the 5000 model variants that best agree with the observational metrics used in that study. In contrast, the N_d - L slope constraint retains all model variants whose simulated slope lies within $\pm 10\%$ of the observed slope estimate. Previous studies show that the N_d - L relationship exhibits substantial variability across regions, meteorological regimes, and retrieval assumptions (Gryspeerd et al., 2019, 2022), but no robust global uncertainty estimate for the slope has been established. We therefore adopt the $\pm 10\%$ threshold as an optimistic, proof-of-concept constraint to assess the potential for constraint under favourable assumptions about observational uncertainty.

The number of retained variants differs between clusters. For the slope constraint, 18 551 variants are retained in NEA, 64 779 in ETA, and 12 026 in SEP. For the combined constraint, we define the retained set as the intersection between model variants satisfying the $\pm 10\%$ slope criterion and the 5000 variants retained by the R23 optimal constraint. This leaves 623 variants in NEA and 1054 in ETA, while no variants satisfy both constraints in SEP. The small number of retained variants in the combined case reflects the stringency of applying both constraints simultaneously and likely represents an over-constrained scenario; however, it still provides useful insight into the compatibility of the two approaches. A summary of the constraint cases and the unconstrained baseline is provided in Table 1.

2.6 Sensitivity analysis

To quantify how the causes of uncertainty in simulated ΔF_{aci} change under different constraints, we use a Generalized Additive Model (GAM) approach following Regayre et al. (2026) and Prévost et al. (2026). Non-linear GAMs are fitted to emulated ΔF_{aci} values separately for each month and cluster using the `pygam` Python package (Servén et al., 2018). GAMs are well

Table 1. Summary of constraint cases evaluated in this study.

Case	Constraint case	Observational basis	Definition and context
1	Unconstrained	None	Baseline emulated parameter space representing prior uncertainty across the 37-dimensional parameter space, identical to the reference cases used in Regayre et al. (2023, 2026).
2	N_d-L slope	Satellite-derived N_d-L slopes from MODIS	Process-based constraint retaining all model variants whose simulated slopes lie within $\pm 10\%$ of the observed slope in each cluster.
3	R23	Global and regional cloud and radiation observations	State-variable-based constraint based on the optimally constrained parameter space identified in Regayre et al. (2023).
4	Combined	N_d-L slope and R23	Intersection of the slope-based and R23.

suiting to this analysis because they capture high-dimensional, non-linear dependencies between parameters and ΔF_{aci} , and remain robust when observational constraints reduce or truncate the sampled parameter space.

For each case (unconstrained and constrained), we assess the marginal influence of individual parameters on ΔF_{aci} by perturbing one parameter at a time while holding all others fixed at the median of the retained model variants. The resulting variation in the GAM-predicted output is used to estimate parameter sensitivities. We quantify parameter importance using a variance-based sensitivity analysis (Strong et al., 2014). For each case, we compute the variance in the GAM-predicted ΔF_{aci} associated with perturbations in each parameter, and normalise by the total variance across all parameters. This yields the fractional contribution of each parameter to the total uncertainty.

For interpretation, we group parameters into aerosol-related and cloud-related categories based on their primary process influence. Aerosol-related parameters relate to aerosol emissions, size distributions, or chemical processes, while cloud-related parameters primarily influence cloud microphysical or macrophysical processes. Some parameters influence both aerosol and cloud processes, but are assigned to the category corresponding to their dominant effect. This classification is intended as an interpretive framework rather than a strict separation of processes.

In addition, we compute probability density functions (PDFs) for all 37 input parameters under each case to characterise how the sampled parameter space changes under constraint. The variance-based sensitivity analysis and parameter PDFs provide complementary information on how constraints modify both the model outputs and the sources of remaining uncertainty.

3 Results

3.1 Regional comparison of constraint effects

Figure 4. Seasonal and monthly variability in (a–c) droplet number concentration (N_d), (d–f) liquid water path (L), (g–i) aerosol–cloud radiative forcing (ΔF_{aci}), and (j–l) N_d – L slope before and after constraint, across the three characteristic clusters: North-East Atlantic (NEA), East-Tropical Atlantic (ETA), and South-East Pacific (SEP). Shaded envelopes represent the full range of uncertainty in the one-million-member set of model variants and the subset of variants from each constraint. Orange circles show observed monthly or seasonal mean values from satellite retrievals.

Figure 5. Distribution of N_d , L , ΔF_{aci} , and N_d-L slope across the NEA, ETA, and SEP clusters. N_d , L , and ΔF_{aci} are shown for January and July, while N_d-L slopes are shown for DJF and JJA. Box plots represent emulator-sampled distributions (interquartile range with 5th–95th percentile whiskers).

The slope constraint (case 2 in Table 1) strongly reduces uncertainty in the N_d-L relationship, as expected, but translates only weakly to reductions in ΔF_{aci} unless combined with the state-variable-based constraint. Figures 4 and 5 show these effects across the three marine clusters. As described in the methods, no combined constraint is available for the SEP because no model variants satisfy both the slope and R23 criteria simultaneously.

In the unconstrained case (grey), N_d shows large regional variability and substantial spread (Fig. 4a–c). Across the annual cycle, the full range of uncertainty in monthly mean N_d across the PPE reaches around 420 cm^{-3} in the NEA, 480 cm^{-3} in the ETA, and 280 cm^{-3} in the SEP. The boxplots in Fig. 5a–c show that this corresponds to wide 90% confidence intervals (CI) in both January and July. For example, in January the 90% CI spans 36.2 to 207.2 cm^{-3} in the NEA, 40.2 to 202.1 cm^{-3} in the ETA, and 53.4 to 178.8 cm^{-3} in the SEP. In July, the corresponding intervals are 42.3 to 230.2 cm^{-3} in the NEA, 41.0 to 259.4 cm^{-3} in the ETA, and 136.4 to 200.5 cm^{-3} in the SEP. The slope constraint has only a weak effect on these

distributions. In the NEA it slightly reduces the upper range, for example reducing the July 90% CI from 42.3 – 230.2 to 44.2 – 224.2 cm^{-3} (Fig. 5a). In the ETA it does not constrain N_d and instead broadens the distribution, from 40.2 – 202.1 to 32.5 – 239.7 cm^{-3} in January and from 41.0 – 259.4 to 25.2 – 293.3 cm^{-3} in July (Fig. 5b). In the SEP the slope constraint shifts the distribution toward higher N_d , with the January 90% CI moving from 53.4 – 178.8 to 102.5 – 198.7 cm^{-3} (Fig. 5c). By contrast, the R23 constraint strongly narrows N_d spread in all three regions: in July the 90% CI contracts to 51.6–94.0 cm^{-3} in the NEA, 53.8–105.6 cm^{-3} in the ETA, and 146.7–194.7 cm^{-3} in the SEP. The combined constraint gives July 90% CIs of 54.2–93.6 cm^{-3} in the NEA and 44.3–85.2 cm^{-3} in the ETA; no combined constraint exists in the SEP because no variants satisfy both constraints. Thus, where the combined constraint exists, it provides only modest additional narrowing beyond R23, with the clearest change in the ETA.

Unconstrained L in the PPE spans approximately 70 – 240 g m^{-2} across the three clusters (Fig. 4d–f), with substantial seasonal variation. The slope constraint has little effect on this distribution across all regions: in the NEA, ETA, and SEP the 90% CIs are only weakly modified (Fig. 5d–f). For example, in the NEA in July the 90% CI changes only slightly from 105.7 – 179.0 g m^{-2} in the unconstrained ensemble to 123.0 – 169.7 g m^{-2} under R23, with the mean state remaining centred away from the observational estimate (orange circles). This weak constraint is consistent with the structural inconsistency between L and N_d in UKESM1-A identified by Regayre et al. (2023), meaning that L is not expected to be strongly constrained by the R23 constraint. In contrast, ΔF_{aci} is strongly constrained by R23 which intentionally selected combinations of observations that would optimally constrain ΔF_{aci} . In the NEA in July, the 90% CI narrows from –6.72 to 6.46 W m^{-2} in the unconstrained case to –5.43 to –2.10 W m^{-2} under R23 (Fig. 5g), and in the ETA from –4.29 to 3.84 W m^{-2} to –3.51 to –0.93 W m^{-2} (Fig. 5h). The slope constraint alone leaves ΔF_{aci} effectively unconstrained in the NEA and ETA: in July the NEA CI remains broad at –6.74 to 3.97 W m^{-2} , while in the ETA it widens to –4.38 to 5.83 W m^{-2} . In the SEP, however, the slope constraint is modestly effective, shifting the July 90% CI from –2.80 to 0.65 W m^{-2} to –3.39 to –0.41 W m^{-2} (Fig. 5i).

The impact of the slope constraint is clearest in the slope distributions themselves (Fig. 4j–l; Fig. 5j–l). As expected from the $\pm 10\%$ selection criterion, the slope distribution is tightly constrained in the selected season for each region. In the NEA (DJF), the 90% CI contracts from –0.615 to 0.179 in the unconstrained case to –0.228 to –0.192 in the slope-constrained case (Fig. 5j). In the SEP (also DJF), the 90% CI contracts from –1.671 to –0.324 to –0.439 to –0.421 (Fig. 5l). For the ETA (MAM), the constrained range similarly collapses around the observed value, from approximately –1.33 to 0.79 in the unconstrained ensemble to about –0.20 to 0.00 in the slope-constrained case (Fig. 4k). However, these reductions in slope uncertainty are largely confined to the selected seasons and does not strongly propagate to other seasons or to the state variables and forcing. In the NEA, for example, the JJA slope distribution remains broad despite the strong DJF constraint (Fig. 5j), and in the ETA the MAM constraint does not substantially reduce the broad JJA range (Fig. 4k). Consistent with this, the slope constraint produces only weak reductions in N_d and ΔF_{aci} in the Atlantic clusters. In the SEP, however, the slope constraint has a more noticeable effect on ΔF_{aci} . This is consistent with Regayre et al. (2026), which showed that ΔF_{aci} uncertainty in this region is dominated by physical atmosphere and cloud-process parameters. The N_d – L slope shares sensitivity to these processes more strongly in the SEP than in the Atlantic clusters, allowing the slope constraint to more effectively reduce forcing uncertainty there.

Figures 4 and 5 show that the state-variable and slope constraints have complementary effects where a combined constraint exists. The R23 constraint primarily reduces uncertainty in N_d and ΔF_{aci} , which complements the N_d-L slope constraint. The combined constraint (case 4 in Table 1) selects model variants that are simultaneously consistent with the large-scale state variables and with the observed process-level relationship. In the NEA, the combined constraint produces only small additional narrowing beyond R23: for example, in July the N_d 90% CI changes from 51.6 – 94.0 cm^{-3} under R23 to 54.2 – 93.6 cm^{-3} under the combined constraint, while ΔF_{aci} remains similar, changing from –5.43 to –2.10 W m^{-2} under R23 to –5.70 to –2.17 W m^{-2} . In the ETA, the combined constraint has a clearer additional effect, narrowing the July N_d range from 53.8 – 105.6 cm^{-3} under R23 to 44.3–85.2 cm^{-3} , and the July ΔF_{aci} range from –3.51 to –0.93 W m^{-2} to –2.69 to –0.52 W m^{-2} . The combined constraint also retains the strong reduction in slope uncertainty imposed by the slope constraint, with the slope distribution remaining tightly centred around the observed value in the constrained season. No combined constraint is available in the SEP, because no model variants satisfy both the R23 and slope criteria, indicating that the two constraints are less compatible than in other regions. Achieving a combined constraint would require relaxing constraint criteria to retain a larger number of model variants (Prévost et al., 2026).

Our results show that in Atlantic regions, the process-based and state-variable-based constraints provide complementary, rather than interchangeable, information about aerosol–cloud interactions that produces a tighter constrain on ΔF_{aci} uncertainty than either achieves independently. However, the R23 constraint is the primary driver of reductions in ΔF_{aci} uncertainty, while the N_d-L slope constrains the underlying process relationship but has a more modest impact on forcing in most regions. Even in the combined constraint, substantial forcing uncertainty remains. For example, the July 90% CI under R23 is reduced to about 25% of the unconstrained width in the NEA, about 32% in the ETA, and about 53% in the SEP. This regional pattern is consistent with Regayre et al. (2026), in which the SEP remains the least constrained region, of the three evaluated here, reflecting the different parametric drivers of uncertainty there.

Figure 6. Causes of cluster-mean ΔF_{aci} uncertainty in the unconstrained and constrained cases for (a) NEA, (b) ETA, and (c) SEP, across four representative months: (i) January, (ii) April, (iii) July, and (iv) October. Percentage contributions to variance are derived from GAM-based sensitivity analyses. Bar segments represent individual parameters, coloured by type (orange–green shades for aerosol-related and purple–blue shades for cloud-related parameters). Numerical labels correspond to parameter indices listed in the right-hand legends, with numbers placed inside bars for parameters contributing more than 5% to the total uncertainty. All values are normalised to 100% per cluster, constraint type and month.

To understand how each constraint reduces uncertainty in ΔF_{aci} , we analyse the contributions of individual model parameters to the variance in cluster-mean forcing. We find that the N_d - L slope constraint primarily reduces the contribution of parameters associated with cloud processes (purple/blue in Fig. 6), while the R23 constraint reduces the contribution of parameters associated with aerosol processes (orange/red in Fig. 6). When both constraints are applied, the contributions from all parameters are reduced to only a few percent of the remaining uncertainty suggesting multiple additional observational constraints may be required to further reduce this uncertainty. Possibly, these constraints are nearing the maximum feasible limit on what is possible with a structurally deficient model.

Figure 6 shows the contribution of individual parameters to ΔF_{aci} uncertainty for the unconstrained and constrained cases across the three clusters, for four representative months (January, April, July, and October). Contributions are derived from GAM-based sensitivity analysis and are normalised to 100% for each cluster, month, and case. The full annual cycle is shown in Figs. S9–S11.

In the unconstrained set of model variants, aerosol-related parameters dominate ΔF_{aci} uncertainty in both the NEA and ETA. In the NEA, parameters controlling primary sulfate mode diameter (`prim_so4_diam`, ~ 25 – 30%), sea spray emissions (`sea_spray`, ~ 8 – 10%), and dimethyl sulfide emissions (`dms`, ~ 7 – 9%) together account for around 40–45% of the total uncertainty. In the ETA, these same parameters contribute more strongly, with `prim_so4_diam` accounting for ~ 30 – 35% and `dms` contributing ~ 10 – 15% . These results are consistent with previous PPE studies (Regayre et al., 2023, 2026), which identified these parameters as key drivers of aerosol–cloud interaction uncertainty.

In the SEP, the contribution of parameters associated with cloud processes is larger than in the NEA and ETA. Cloud-related parameters account for approximately 45–50% of the total uncertainty, compared to around 50–55% from aerosol-related parameters. The largest individual contributors include the updraft velocity parameter (`sig_w`, ~ 12 – 15%) and the cloud–rain spatial correlation parameter (`c_r_correl`, ~ 6 – 10%). This reflects the stronger influence of cloud and boundary-layer processes in the stratocumulus regime, although aerosol-related parameters still account for a substantial fraction of the total uncertainty.

Applying the N_d - L slope constraint changes the relative contribution of parameters to the remaining uncertainty. In the NEA and ETA, the remaining uncertainty is dominated by a small number of aerosol parameters, particularly `prim_so4_diam`, which contributes approximately 70–85% of the remaining variance. At the same time, the contribution from parameters associated with cloud processes is substantially reduced. This behaviour is consistent with the slope constraint primarily reducing uncertainty in cloud-process parameters.

In the SEP, the effect of the slope constraint on parameter contributions is smaller. The fraction of remaining uncertainty associated with parameters linked to cloud processes decreases slightly in most months (from ~ 50 – 55% to ~ 40 – 45%), although the change is small compared to the NEA and ETA. Therefore, the slope constraint reduces the influence of some cloud-related parameters in SEP, but the relative contributions remain more balanced between aerosol and cloud processes than in the Atlantic clusters.

The R23 constraint has a different effect on the parameters. In both the NEA and ETA, the contribution of `prim_so4_diam` decreases from ~ 25 – 35% in the unconstrained case to $\sim 10\%$, while other aerosol parameters such as `dms` and `sea_spray`

increase to $\sim 15\text{--}20\%$. At the same time, parameters associated with cloud processes, including the cloud-top entrainment parameter (`a_ent_1_rp`), increase in relative importance to around $10\text{--}15\%$. This indicates that the R23 constraint reduces uncertainty associated with aerosol size and emissions, leaving a larger fraction of the remaining uncertainty associated with cloud and boundary-layer processes. This behaviour is consistent with the annual-mean analysis in Regayre et al. (2026),
355 although here we show that similar patterns hold on monthly timescales.

In the SEP, the R23 constraint affects the balance of cloud-related and aerosol-related contributions to the remaining ΔF_{aci} uncertainty, particularly in April, July, and October. The total contribution from cloud-related parameters changes from approximately 50% in the unconstrained case to 41% after R23 in April, remains close to 50% in both cases in July, and decreases from approximately 43% to 36% in October. Aerosol-related parameters such as `dms` and `sea_spray` also remain
360 important after R23. This indicates that the R23 constraint uses observational information in the SEP that is related to both cloud and aerosol processes. However, the cloud-related behaviour favoured by R23 is inconsistent with that favoured by the $N_d\text{--}L$ slope constraint in this region, explaining why no model variants satisfy both constraints under our default constraint process.

When both constraints are applied together (where possible), the contribution from all parameters is reduced. In the NEA
365 and ETA, most individual parameters contribute only a few percent to the remaining uncertainty, with no single parameter dominating. This reflects the fact that the two constraints act on different aspects of the model: the slope constraint primarily reduces uncertainty associated with cloud processes, while the R23 constraint reduces uncertainty associated with aerosol processes. Together, they limit the range of parameter combinations that are associated with observations.

In principle, the $N_d\text{--}L$ slope might be expected to influence both aerosol- and cloud-related parameters, since it links aerosol-
370 driven changes in droplet number to subsequent adjustments in liquid water path. However, we find that its impact is largely confined to parameters associated with cloud processes, with comparatively little reduction in the contribution of aerosol-related parameters to ΔF_{aci} uncertainty. This suggests that the coupling between aerosol and cloud processes, as expressed through the perturbed parameters in this PPE, is not sufficiently strong for a process-based constraint on $N_d\text{--}L$ to propagate effectively across both components of the system. As a result, a substantial fraction of the remaining uncertainty associated
375 with aerosol-related parameters remains unconstrained. This limits the effectiveness of the slope constraint in reducing ΔF_{aci} when applied in isolation. The R23 state-variable constraint typically reduces uncertainty associated with aerosol processes, leading to a stronger reduction in ΔF_{aci} uncertainty. When both constraints are applied together, the contributions from both groups of parameters are reduced, resulting in the smallest remaining uncertainty. This supports the interpretation that process-based and state-variable-based constraints provide complementary information about the causes of ΔF_{aci} uncertainty and act
380 on different sets of parameters.

3.3 Link between N_d and L and implications for constraints

The results from section 3.1 show that the $N_d\text{--}L$ slope constrained by the R23 state variables is systematically more negative than observed (Fig. 4I). Satellite-based estimates of the $N_d\text{--}L$ slope typically fall between -0.5 and -0.1 in marine regions (Gryspeerd et al., 2019). In this study, the unconstrained PPE produces a wide range of slopes (e.g. from about -0.6 to 0.2

385 in NEA DJF) that includes the observational range. The slope-constrained PPE is tightly centred around these values in the
selected season (e.g. -0.23 to -0.19 in NEA DJF and -0.20 to 0.00 in ETA MAM; Fig. 4j–l; Fig. 5j–l). By contrast, the values
produced by the R23 constraint are much more negative, ranging from -0.5 to -2.0 in the ETA cluster and -0.6 to -2.2 in
the SEP. This difference likely arises because the R23 constraint primarily targets large-scale aerosol and cloud state variables
that are directly sensitive to N_d (e.g., hemispheric contrasts in droplet number and radiative fluxes), but does not explicitly
390 constrain the cloud liquid water response to changes in N_d . This highlights structural limitations in the model and missing
links between N_d and L in the model formulation, as previously identified by Regayre et al. (2023). The UKESM1 model
uses single-moment cloud microphysics, with only the cloud water mass being prognosed, while N_d is diagnosed separately.
As a result, cloud water removal processes (e.g., through precipitation or entrainment) do not feed back onto N_d , effectively
decoupling N_d and L . This decoupling is most clearly seen in the SEP cluster (Fig. 4l), where the slope values associated
395 with model variants constrained by the N_d – L slope and R23 observations do not overlap in most seasons. By contrast, in the
NEA and ETA clusters, some overlap is observed, suggesting that indirect links may exist between the two variables, though
possibly not for the right reasons.

3.3.1 Processes linking N_d and L

Figure 7. Emergent thermodynamic pathway linking N_d and L across the PPE for NEA cluster in winter months (DJF). Panels (a,c,e) show joint probability distributions of specific humidity (q) as a function of N_d for three representative PPE members, with separate linear fits for low- N_d (blue) and high- N_d (red) regimes. Panels (b,d,f) show joint probability distributions of L as a function of $1/q$ for the same members. Reported slopes (m_l , m_h) indicate low- and high-regime sensitivities. Panels (g,h) show the probability density functions of the fitted slopes across all 221 PPE members.

Figure 7 demonstrates that, across the 221-member PPE, N_d and L are indirectly linked through specific humidity (q). Joint probability distributions of individual PPE members show that increasing N_d is systematically associated with decreasing q (Fig. 7a,c,e), with this inverse relationship evident across both low- and high- N_d regimes. Conversely, q is strongly and consistently linked to liquid water path, with L increasing as q increases (Fig. 7b,d,f). These relationships suggest an indirect N_d - q - L pathway. We hypothesise that this reflects co-variability between aerosol, thermodynamic, and cloud processes across the PPE, rather than a direct causal chain linking N_d and L (Mikkelsen et al., 2025).

The probability density functions of fitted slopes across all PPE members (Fig. 7g,h) show that both the inverse N_d - q relationship and the positive q - L relationship are common across many PPE members, although their magnitude varies substantially between members and regimes. This variability highlights a key advantage of the PPE framework where emergent relationships can be diagnosed statistically across hundreds of model variants but would be difficult to isolate from a single model configuration. This indirect coupling provides a physically interpretable explanation for several features identified in earlier sections. The humidity-mediated cloud response allows the N_d - L slope constraint to reduce uncertainty in the slope itself without necessarily constraining N_d or ΔF_{aci} . This occurs because the slope constraint preferentially rules out model variants associated with cloud susceptibility to aerosol mediated by humidity rather than directly constraining aerosol emissions or radiative responses. It also clarifies why the R23 constraint, which is based on matching large-scale cloud and radiation state variables, can constrain N_d -related metrics while leaving substantial freedom in L , since although q influences both variables, R23 does not explicitly target the thermodynamic pathway linking them and physical atmosphere parameters therefore remain weakly constrained (Regayre et al., 2026).

Finally, this indirect link between N_d and L helps explain why the slope and R23 constraints are consistent in some regions but not in others. In the SEP cluster, where stratocumulus clouds are strongly controlled by boundary-layer thermodynamics, variability in L is dominated by thermodynamic factors. As a result, the N_d - q - L pathway leads to a clear separation between model variants that satisfy the slope constraint and those that satisfy the R23 constraint. In contrast, in the NEA and ETA clusters, there is partial overlap between the sets of model variants that satisfy each constraint. This indicates that, in these regions, changes in aerosol, thermodynamics, and cloud properties are more closely coupled within the model. However, this agreement does not necessarily arise from physically realistic feedbacks, but may instead reflect compensating effects between parameters. These results demonstrate that the inconsistency between N_d and L under the R23 constraint arises from the absence of a direct physical coupling between these variables in the model, with their relationship instead mediated by thermodynamic variability. This highlights the importance of thermodynamic controls in aerosol-cloud interactions and shows how process-based diagnostics within a PPE can be used to identify structural limitations in the model formulation.

3.3.2 Inconsistent parameter constraints

Figure 8. Marginal probability density functions (PDFs) of four key model parameters: `prim_so4_diam`, `dms`, `sig_w`, and `a_ent_1_rp`, shown under four constraint cases: unconstrained (grey), N_d -L slope (blue), R23 (green), and combined constraint (purple). Distributions are presented for the Northeast Atlantic (NEA; panels a–d), Eastern Tropical Atlantic (ETA; panels e–h), and Southeast Pacific (SEP; panels i–l) clusters. Vertical dashed lines indicate the median of each distribution.

The results in Section 3.1 showed that the N_d -L slope and R23 constraints retain different sets of model variants, with no
 430 overlap in the SEP cluster. We next examine the parameter values associated with each retained set to diagnose how the two
 constraints differ in their effects on the ensemble. Figure 8 shows marginal probability density functions for selected aerosol-
 and cloud-related parameters under the unconstrained and constrained cases, evaluated separately for the NEA, ETA, and SEP
 clusters (see Supplement Figs. S9–S11 for all 37 parameters). These distributions show how each constraint restricts the range
 of plausible parameter values and whether consistent parameter ranges can satisfy both constraints simultaneously.

435 Overall, the parameter distributions associated with model variants that satisfy the N_d - L slope constraint are distinct from those that satisfy the R23 constraint. In many cases, the slope-constrained distributions remain similar to the unconstrained distributions, indicating that the slope constraint exerts only a weak influence on several parameters (e.g. `dms` in panels b, f, and j). Where the slope constraint does modify parameter distributions, it often constrains parameters towards values different from those favoured by the R23 constraint. This suggests that the two constraints act on different parts of parameter space and
440 is consistent with the structural inconsistencies identified in Regayre et al. (2023).

This contrast is particularly evident for the aerosol size parameter `prim_so4_diam` and the cloud droplet activation parameter `sig_w`. The R23 constraint shifts `prim_so4_diam` towards larger values in all clusters (median normalised value ~ 0.6 – 0.7 , equivalent to approximately 61–71 nm; panels a, e, i), consistent with lower droplet number concentrations required to match observed cloud and radiative states. In contrast, the slope constraint favours smaller values of `prim_so4_diam`
445 (median normalised values ~ 0.3 – 0.4 in the ETA and SEP, equivalent to approximately 32–42 nm; panels e and i), consistent with higher N_d and weaker (less negative) N_d - L slopes. This opposing behaviour illustrates the type of tension described by Prévost et al. (2026); Regayre et al. (2023), where different observational constraints favour incompatible regions of parameter space. For other parameters, broad overlap between constrained and unconstrained distributions persists (e.g. `dms` and `a_ent_1_rp`), indicating equifinality: multiple combinations of aerosol and cloud parameters can reproduce observed
450 relationships with similar skill (Lee et al., 2016), yet may lead to divergent responses under future climate conditions (Peace et al., 2020).

These results show that the N_d - L slope constraint provides information about ΔF_{aci} uncertainty that is largely independent of the R23 constraint and is particularly effective at constraining parameters linked to cloud processes. However, the lack of overlap between constraints in some regions highlights that this information cannot be fully exploited within the current
455 model framework. The inconsistency arises from structural limitations in the representation of aerosol–cloud interactions, most notably the use of single-moment microphysics, which prevents a physically consistent coupling between N_d and L . Addressing these structural deficiencies is therefore essential for combining process-based and state-variable-based constraints to more effectively reduce uncertainty in aerosol–cloud interactions.

3.4 Seasonal variability in ΔF_{aci} constraint

Table 2. Reduction in the 90 % confidence interval (CI) of monthly mean ΔF_{aci} relative to the unconstrained set of model variants (%), shown for each constraint case, cluster, and month. The additional reduction achieved by the combined constraint relative to the R23 constraint (Combined – R23) is shown as ‘Gain over R23’.

Month	NEA				ETA				SEP	
	Slope	R23	Combined	Gain over R23	Slope	R23	Combined	Gain over R23	Slope	R23
January	7.8	58.5	77.2	18.7	4.1	68.5	73.7	5.2	41.6	47.7
February	6.0	77.4	81.7	4.3	0.9	71.9	83.1	11.2	16.5	52.9
March	0.0	76.8	81.7	4.9	5.9	71.8	82.2	10.4	26.8	58.4
April	1.1	78.4	82.7	4.3	4.5	75.2	82.6	7.4	24.8	58.2
May	2.5	75.8	82.9	7.1	1.4	71.2	84.4	13.2	28.3	66.5
June	0.9	70.7	81.2	10.5	0.0	68.5	79.1	10.6	26.7	72.1
July	1.5	73.6	82.2	8.6	0.0	65.7	82.4	16.7	31.3	67.4
August	4.9	75.0	82.6	7.6	2.2	70.9	82.9	12.0	29.4	65.8
September	3.3	75.7	82.1	6.4	4.7	69.2	82.1	12.9	31.3	63.1
October	1.4	73.1	84.2	11.1	5.1	72.7	81.1	8.4	29.0	65.1
November	12.9	35.1	71.6	36.5	6.0	44.7	68.2	23.5	29.2	42.7
December	5.3	59.7	76.0	16.3	7.4	32.2	63.8	31.6	21.8	27.8

460 Table 2 shows the monthly reduction in the 90 % confidence interval (CI) of ΔF_{aci} relative to the unconstrained ensemble. The main feature is the relatively weak seasonal variability in the R23 constraint over much of the annual cycle. In the NEA, R23 reduces the monthly ΔF_{aci} CI by 71 – 78 % from February to October, while in the ETA the corresponding reductions are 66 – 75 %. In the SEP, reductions are generally 58 – 72 % from March to October. This suggests that the parameters constrained by R23 influence ΔF_{aci} in a broadly consistent way through most of the year, rather than only under specific
465 seasonal meteorological conditions.

The main exception occurs in the winter and early-winter months. The R23 constraint is weakest in November in the NEA (35 %), in December in the ETA (32 %), and in December in the SEP (28 %). January is also among the weaker months in the NEA and SEP, with reductions of 59 % and 48 %, respectively. This reduced constraint may reflect the fact that the R23 optimal constraint is based on a small set of state-variable observations selected for their ability to constrain annual/global ΔF_{aci} , rather
470 than specifically targeting monthly forcing in each of the three clusters considered here. Although the R23 optimal set includes observations from several seasons, including December Southern Ocean N_d and transect-based cloud-property relationships, the selected observations do not necessarily constrain the parameter dependencies that dominate wintertime ΔF_{aci} in the NEA, ETA, and SEP.

By comparison, the N_d – L slope constraint has little seasonal impact on ΔF_{aci} uncertainty in the NEA and ETA, with
475 reductions generally below 10 %. The slope constraint is more effective in the SEP, where reductions range from 17 % to 42 %,

consistent with the larger role of cloud-related parameters in this stratocumulus regime. However, it remains weaker than R23 in every month. Where the slope and R23 constraints can be combined, the combined constraint gives the largest reductions, especially in months where R23 alone is relatively weak. For example, the gain over R23 is 36.5 % in the NEA in November and 31.6 % in the ETA in December.

480 4 Conclusions

We assessed the effectiveness of a process-based observational constraint derived from the slope of the relationship between cloud droplet number concentration (N_d) and liquid water path (L) in constraining uncertainty in aerosol–cloud radiative forcing (ΔF_{aci}) using a perturbed parameter ensemble (PPE) of the UKESM1 model. The slope constraint was evaluated across three climatically distinct marine regions and compared with a state-variable-based constraint derived from observed
485 cloud and radiation properties (Regayre et al., 2023), as well as with a combined application of both approaches.

Analysis of multiple PPE members reveals that the N_d – L relationship in the model does not arise from a direct microphysical coupling between droplet number and cloud water, but instead from their shared dependence on thermodynamic variability, particularly specific humidity. Across the ensemble, N_d and L covary through meteorological variability in humidity rather than through an explicit causal pathway in the model formulation. While this relationship should not be interpreted as a
490 physically complete representation of aerosol–cloud processes (Mikkelsen et al., 2025), it remains informative within a PPE framework. As with other observational constraints applied in PPE studies (Lee et al., 2016; Johnson et al., 2020; Regayre et al., 2023, 2026), the N_d – L slope is best viewed as a diagnostic of how parameter perturbations influence observable relationships. In practice, this means that the slope can help rule out parameter combinations that produce unrealistic process-level behaviour, even when the model does not represent the underlying causal pathways completely.

Our results show that the N_d – L slope provides useful additional information, but does not substantially reduce uncertainty
495 in ΔF_{aci} when applied in isolation. In aerosol-rich regions such as the Northeast and Eastern Tropical Atlantic, multiple combinations of aerosol and cloud parameters produce similar N_d – L relationships that agree with observed slopes, limiting the efficacy of the slope as a constraint on aerosol forcing. In the aerosol-limited Southeast Pacific, the slope constraint has a stronger influence on parameter distributions, but often pushes aerosol-related parameters towards values different from those
500 favoured by the R23 constraint. These limitations reflect both equifinality and structural deficiencies in the model, particularly the weak coupling between droplet number and cloud water in the single-moment microphysics scheme. As a result, satisfying the observed N_d – L relationship does not necessarily imply consistency with observed cloud states or radiative fluxes. When applied alongside the R23 state-variable constraint, the slope can further reduce ΔF_{aci} uncertainty in some regions, indicating that it provides complementary information. However, the combined constraint also exposes where agreement with multiple
505 observational metrics may arise for the wrong reasons, rather than from a physically consistent representation of aerosol–cloud interactions.

These results should be interpreted in the context of observational uncertainty. Our analysis represents an idealised case in which uncertainty in the observed N_d – L slope is assumed to be very low ($\pm 10\%$). In practice, robustly estimating this slope

from aggregated satellite observations is challenging, and the associated uncertainty may substantially weaken its effective
510 constraining power. While we demonstrate that the slope has the potential to reduce uncertainty and to expose key structural
limitations in current models, real-world application will require more precise observational estimates and explicit treatment
of uncertainty propagation.

In summary, the N_d - L slope provides valuable diagnostic insight into the parameter sensitivities and structural behaviour
of aerosol–cloud interactions in climate models, but it cannot be used in isolation to robustly constrain ΔF_{aci} . Its greatest
515 value lies within multi-constraint frameworks that combine process-level diagnostics with state-variable consistency. Realising
this potential will require improved model structure, particularly stronger coupling between aerosol and cloud processes, for
example through the adoption of two-moment microphysics schemes (Shipway and Hill, 2012; Field et al., 2023).

. **Code availability:** Code used to create the figures in this article is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19923874>.

. **Data availability:** Output from the A-CURE PPE is available from the Centre for Environmental Data Analysis (CEDA) archive at
520 <https://catalogue.ceda.ac.uk/uuid/b735718d66c1403fbf6b93ba3bd3b1a9> (Regayre et al., 2021).

. **Author Contributions:** KG led the research, processed output from the ensemble, applied the statistical emulators using code developed
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means clustering used to define the regional analysis and contributed to manuscript editing and interpretation. The constraint framework
525 and experimental design were developed by KG with input from LR and KC. KC provided overall scientific direction and supervision. The
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